

Somaliland Minority: Gaboye Communities' Needs and Living Conditions

Bulsho Minority Humanitarian Development & Initiatives BMHDI

Email address:

**nation00003@gmail.com/bsdo.hargeisa.
gmail.com**

Office Tel: +252633203729

**Ida'ada bus stand, Near Hargeisa National Cinema, 26June,
Hargeisa, Somaliland
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Author: Abdinasir Hassan Muhumed Timoweyne

Executive Director of BMHDI

Cell phone: m+252634403296

Email: nation00003@gmail.com

To the readers

This assessment, which is our own work (not palagrarism) and was conducted voluntarily and is based on facts and the truth, has been published in order to raise the voice of Somaliland's marginalised minority communities. It is still draft and needs to be reviewed and edited on a voluntary basis. There is also a need to fund conferences for its presentation in Somaliland's six regions.

Anvone is welcome to contribute.

Table of contents

Somaliland Minority: Gaboye Communities' Needs and Living Conditions 1

Bulsho Minority Humanitarian Development & Initiatives BMHDI 1

Somaliland Minority: Gaboye Communities' Needs and Living Conditions 4

Overview 4

Introduction 4

The method of gathering information 6

Population 7

Strengths and limitations 7

Findings 8

Conclusion 19

Recommendation 19

Acknowledgement 20

World Vision 21

Advocacy 21

Supply of school and office equipment 21

Health: Treat Mohamed Khadar Said 22

Dahabshil Bank 22

MOELSA, under the Abdirashid, DG 22

Team of the Assessment 22

About the study 24

Questionnaire 25

Focus group discussion 29

About BMHDI

BULSHO is a LNNGO of its kind established by members of minority individuals working in the area to voice out range persisted problems of discrimination and isolations that deprived minority communities in Somaliland from their social, economic and political rights. BULSHO envision working with and addressing the needs of the minority group/society through promotion of their human rights and socioeconomic development by strengthening their capacities, skills and knowledge to enable them attain sustainable development.

Mission

BULSHO is committed to work to contribute to the creation of equitable and inclusive society through the elimination of case-based discrimination and untouchability through providing the disadvantaged and marginalized minority people with the tools needed to deal with their social, educational, environmental, healthy, economic and cultural issues and concerns

Assessment 2 2022

Somaliland Minority: Gaboye Communities' Needs and Living Conditions

Overview

This report is based on an assessment of the Gaboye community's needs and living conditions in Somaliland's four areas of Togdheer, Sahil, Marodi-jeeh, and Awdal in 2022. This brief report emphasizes the precarious status of Somaliland's minority Gaboye community, which has yet to be addressed. This assessment will address the questions, "What are the economic, social, political, and public service barriers that minorities confront in accessing their basic rights to justice and equality, education, health, water, power, roads, and so on?" We will investigate how these communities connect and share with other Somaliland communities, as well as public services, government development plans, political engagement and job opportunities, and international aid.

Introduction

Minority clan groups in Somali territory are numerous and concentrated throughout the Somali peninsula. As a result, this study focuses on the minority and disenfranchised Gabooye clans of Somaliland, who have suffered greatly as a result of the majority's persecution. Discrimination is the only reason these people have been unable to share with other Somalis, obtain basic rights, and have become minorities and marginalized. The aim of this work is not to explain why they are discriminated against, but inexperienced readers may question whether the Gaboye minority is distinct from the rest of Somalis, such as a separate ethnic group, but discrimination against the Gabooye clans does not take place on the basis of religion or ethnicity. Both

the majority (Aji) main clans and the minority (Gobeeye) clans are of the same ethnicity (same culture, same color, same religion, and same language).

The reasons for these people's discrimination are inherited or passed down from generation to generation through traditional oral stories. There are various tails or stories concerning why these minority communities are discriminated against, and each of them is thought to be unreliable because they are based on hearsay or only myths. However, it is undeniable that it is influenced by the culture.

Because Somalis traditionally reside in rival clans, it appears that a set of clans (the majority) culturally agreed to isolate other clan groups, which eventually became minorities. The majority clans, who believe they are superior, were prejudiced against this group of minority people to the point where it became conventional law not to engage with them in any form, including friendship, marriage, labor, and so on. Individuals from so-called majority communities only interact with these folks once, and that is when they are following their own interests.

Individuals in the majority were persuaded to discriminate against these people because, as they allege, they misbehaved. Certain slanderous accusations allege that they are discriminated against because they used to eat dead animals, which Islam forbids, and that they deceived the Islamic religion, particularly in marriage.

One of the tales goes as follows:-

Two men, one from the minority clans, who were not used to be discriminated at the time, and one from the dominant clans, journeyed together. They became disoriented on the way. They were hungry after a long and exhausting day. They also didn't have anything to eat. They

happened to come across a dead animal. They were both starving, so they devoured the carcass. When they arrived at their destination seven days later, one of the men from the majority clan made himself puke, but the other refused, stating he couldn't make himself vomit what he had eaten before seven days. On that day, the man was accused of breaking culture since he refused to force himself to vomit. As a result, he had to face discrimination. The two men, as the tale goes, are the ancestors of the majority and minority clans. The truth is that neither party has the same father. This means that the clans known as the majority do not have the same father, despite the fact that the majority is the same.

According to some accounts, they defrauded the Islamic religion, particularly in marriage. Another narrative goes like this:-

Once upon a time, these individuals were treated the same as everyone else, but they were dismissed because they made a mistake regarding their religion. From these tribes, there was a sheikh named Mohamed Haniif who commanded the Somali territories. This sheikh used to take advantage of couples who wanted to marry each other. Before making the couples marry, he would impose a condition on them. He used to have seven days of carnal intercourse with each bride. After that, he would marry the woman to the man. Finally, because the objective of this assessment is not to explain the precise reason for the discrimination, we will leave this subject to other assessments.

[The method of gathering information](#)

This data was used to conduct interviews with people, including committee members, who are extensively involved in monitoring the situation and needs of these areas and for focus group discussion.

Population

In total, 200 people from the four regions took part in this interview. However, only 40 of the 200 people examined were interviewed directly. The 160 other interviewees came in at the back door. They were given the choice of agreeing or disagreeing with any question posed to the 40 interviewees. They were also given the opportunity to share their ideas. They did, however, typically agree with all of the comments supplied by the 40 interviewees. There was also a focus group discussion with ten¹ people from the four regions participating. The interview and focus group discussions yielded all of the information required.

Strengths and limitations

Both the assessment team and the people are from the same communities, so the evaluators have to experience the living conditions of the community, and this increases the accuracy and reliability of the findings. The method was riddled with both strengths and limitations. The strengths outweighed the weaknesses. The assessment team, on the other hand, found the participants to be highly receptive. However, because the participants were unable to read or write, we were unable to distribute questionnaires, which would have greatly benefited the assessment. As a result, a team of two people was assigned the duty of completing out the questionnaires by interview.

¹ **Group discussion members were:** Chief Ahmed Abdi, traditional leader, member of the Dami District Judicial Committee, Tel. +25263 4126568,

Chief Adan Kadaf, traditional leader, traditional leader, member of the Dami District Judicial Committee, Tel. +252634111027

Ubah Abdilahi Hirsi spokeswoman of Dami Women's Committee,

Gudoon Omer Hassan, educated woman, Tel. +25263 4521716

Suldan Maxamuud Xuseen Tel. +252634108704

Osman Arab Hersi, Tel. +252634334253

Abdisaaq husein Mousa, Tel. +252633816182,

Asiya Abdilahi Haji. Tel.25263 4822860,

Layla Dahir Faraax, Tel. +252634456529

Jamac Aarb AHmed Tel. 252634477133

Photo 1. One of the participants, the Deputy Minister of Justice, is shown above in a focus group discussion with Deeq Dahir, the board chair of the Busho Minority Humanitarian Development and Initiative.

Findings

The study's argument is that due to cultural prejudice, these minority communities have been deprived all of their basic rights in the country. These include equity and justice, access to public services, participation in politics and councils, and employment opportunities with the government and non-governmental organizations (INGOs). They also lost their typical work skills, which they had to rely on to make ends meet. The issue is not simply that these concerns exist, but that the Somaliland government and International Organizations have not addressed or neglected them.

We identified the following issues in this assessment:

- In each region, the living conditions for these communities are the same. We discovered this by analyzing data from the four regions of Togdheer, Marodi-jeex, Awdal, and Sahil in 2022.

- These communities rely on their traditional or cultural skills to generate income. These talents, handed from their forefathers and the backbone of their economy, are being ignored, and the government is doing little to develop them. Among these abilities are specializations in footwear, hairdressing, and metal technology. They make metal utensils such as pots, pans, knives, spoons, and farm implements. Nonetheless, they face discrimination in the society in which they live as a result of their skills. As a result of this prejudice, these populations are frequently denied basic human rights from the government, such as political participation, council membership, and senior posts.

One of the most serious issues they have inherited as a result of discrimination is that their typical jobs have declined and they are leaving the market, causing them to become displaced because Somaliland's majority populations believe these skills are for inferior people. The majority of Somaliland or Somali populations recognize that these abilities are possessed by minority communities that are not permitted to engage with the majority, like in marriage. Water is likewise in short supply. Furthermore, there is a scarcity of food. It is because there are no representatives from these groups in government or international organizations who speak for them.

Commercial displacement occurs in the communities where these people live, such as in the Dami market. Dami Market, a vegetable, meat, and other item market, has closed. As a result, small businesses, mostly managed by women, have relocated to Hargeisa's main downtown market. This is after no government attempted to reconstruct it, whereas the government rebuilt any other marks of the same for the majority community after Somaliland's terrible battles.

Ph2. This photograph depicts the market being evacuated because there was no one to care for or maintain it.

- These minority are the poorest communities in Somaliland, and they dwell in the most run-down villages. The following are the locations where they live in each of the four regions: Burao is the capital of the Togdheer region. They dwell in a village called "Urayso" (foul odor) in this city; in the capital of the country, the Marodi-jeex region, they live in Daami village; in Borama, the capital of the Awdal region, they live in Hayayaabe; and in Berbera, the Sahil region, they live in Jama-laye. When you visit these locations, you will notice that they resemble refugee camps. They are the most unsightly and filthy environments where normal life may not be possible. The Somaliland government and foreign organizations, on the other hand, have forgotten about it. Instead of concentrating on the most vulnerable places, they are focusing on other locations that have better living circumstances than them.

The following is the population distribution of these four areas: Daami has settled 3,500 impoverished families. Dami appears to be visually distinct from the other settlements in Hargeisa. It is historic since it was the first IDP settlement in Somaliland since 1954. It is worth noting that the Daami family

Ph2. Members of the Daami community can be seen in this photo attending a focused discussion group.

is mostly made up of returnees from Ethiopian refugee camps, where 2 to 5 families live together. The village committee has frequently said that the needs of the Daami IDPs have not been met, calling it the worst injustice perpetrated by the government and foreign organizations. IDPs from other "majority" areas, for example, were offered permanent homes, but those from "minority" areas were not.

For one hundred years, the pond of Daami was one of the most horrifying sights we saw (balayga Dami). During the rainy season, this pond is enormous and full of water. Although they drink from this pond, people are addicted to tossing trash into it, so it has poor hygiene.

Ph3. This image depicts a mother sobbing for her baby, who was murdered by the well. New about this: <http://www.waaberinews.com/2018/11/01/baliga-daami-oo-liqay-wiil-dhalin-yar-ah-xili-madaxweyne-biixi-hore-amar-uga-bixiyey-baabiinta-dhamamka-hargeysa/>

Excessive hygiene is harmful to the individuals who live nearby, particularly those who attend school and reside around it. When children

try to swim, it can be fatal. The destruction is extensive, and when it

rains, it washes away dwellings. Children will be unable to attend school for months until the pond empties, as it is the only one owned by the community, and the school itself becomes a part of the pond. It also

Ph5. This photo shows the overview of the pond.

produces mosquitos that transmit malaria. The strange thing is that this plague has been around for quite some time, but the government has done little to combat it.

Similarly, the manority communities' shoemakers' center, or "Gabooye clans," was not restructured after the war. Members of the "dominant communities" instead took over a piece of the center's buildings and grounds, while the rest was completely destroyed. As a result, shoemakers make shoes on the streets, but they are involved in car accidents. In contrast, the government rebuilt all public commercial spaces that had been

destroyed throughout the wars, as well as opening new markets for the "Aji clans," or majority populations.

Urayso has settled 1,500 poor families, and Hayayabe, a village in Borama, is home to 350 destitute Gaboye clan families. These settlements are distinct from the rest of the cities since they are populated by impoverished people. Berbera is also home to 800 households, and it is no different from other cities.

Ph6. This image depicts some shoemakers trading in front of a business structure, which is not suited for producing and selling.

Figure 1. This figure depicts the population distribution for each of the four areas.

- The discrimination has had a major impact on these groups in particular, as well as on all aspects of life, and has caused them to keep below the

poverty line and in more difficult circumstances than the people with whom they share the land. Public service, government development plans, political involvement, and job opportunities are all necessary in every society, but they are absent in this minority group. These people are struggling and are subjected to severe inequity and discrimination, which their committees frequently reinforce. This prejudice has had a significant impact on both individual and societal rights. For example, they have no access to work in the government, private sector, or INGOs. It has also kept this group out of government development plans. Job opportunities in the public, non-governmental, and commercial sectors are completely excluded. The government employed six workers in Burao, seven in Borama, one hundred in Hargeisa, and twenty in Berbera, while INGOs had none. Due to the discrimination and treatment of the Gaboye people, they are not able to share work chances.

However, the government's performance is not nothing. One of the important government initiatives has been the involvement of the Ministry of Labor, Social Affairs, and Family Affairs in recruiting persons from these marginalized communities. For example, AbdiRashid, the ministry's director, is in charge of 15 women hired by Hello Trust.

It should also be highlighted that the Somaliland Civil Aviation Authority employs the most

Ph7. This photo shows Members of Bulsho and Abdirashid, the DG of labor, social, and family affairs, discuss employment opportunities for minority communities.

members of these underprivileged populations, with at least 20 individuals working there.

Figure 2. This graph depicts the government's minority employment distribution across four

- These minority and marginalized communities are isolated from the rest of society wherever they live in these four cities. As a result, the public services to which they have access, such as security, education, health, roads, water, and power, are far less tangible when compared to other similar majority-group areas. In terms of education and health, for example, there is no high school at all, and health facilities are extremely limited, and even when they are accessible, they are unable to cover even 10% of the community's needs. These villages are

extremely unsafe in terms of security. In comparison to other villages, crimes are more common, and prostitutes increase by confronting violence and using force. For example, despite the fact that Dami is one of the most dangerous, drug-infested, and prostituted areas in the country, the single police station there is not designed to provide security because there are only six police officers on duty.

- Justice is also unequal. These poor communities are susceptible to harassment at the police station and in the courts, particularly in cases of marriages between members of minority and majority communities.

Consider the instance of Hinda Abdilahi Farah. Hinda is a victim not only of her in-laws, but also of the police stations and courts where she was arrested for marrying a guy from the majority community. Furthermore, following the death of her spouse, both Hinda and her child were denied their share of the property inheritance from her mother-in-law. The

Ph8. This photo shows Bulsho's ED, Abdinasir, interviewing victim Hinda Abdilahi.

case has been ongoing for 12 years, and no resolution has been found. In short, the standard of justice in these locations is extremely low for

these minority people. We could argue that Hargeisa delivered justice 30% of the time, Burao 20% of the time, Borama 30% of the time, and Berbera 20% of the time.

- The burning of the Wahan market in March 2022 is the latest example of discrimination against the Gaboye community. The fire that engulfed the market caused extensive damage and lost property to 200 members of the Gaboye minority. The 200 were among 25 hairdressers who were originally forcibly removed from their businesses in 1991. Of the 200 people including hairdressers, shoemakers, perfumers and fragrance, groceries have not received any support such as money and temporary places to continue their business from the government and non-government organization while others from the majorities were provided resettlement and distribution of funds. Dahabshil Bank loans were used by some of those who lost their businesses in the Wahan market fire. They now have nothing to do and are unable to repay the loan. They now have nothing to do and are unable to repay the loan.

Conclusion

Minorities confront economic, social, political, and public service impediments to their basic rights to justice and equality, education, health, water, power, roads, and so on, as a result of a long-standing cultural stigma towards the Gaboye minority clans. This stigma stems from a long-held idea that the Gaboye clans are evil. The issue is that they are not recognized as human beings but as subhumans. They are also viewed as terrible individuals, the sources of all evil. As a result, the Gaboye minority communities are isolated from the rest of society.

They are either left out of national development plans or those of international organizations; they don't have access to jobs, politics, or civil servants at the regional and district levels. They have reached a point where integration is no longer a possibility, such as when they are not permitted to marry from the majority or be married by the majority. In a nutshell, these people are in a catastrophic humanitarian situation.

Recommendation

Because it is a society that has been discriminated against, it is the lowest and most vulnerable in the country to all kinds of things. As a result, we urge that anyone in charge of developing or implementing Somaliland community development projects begin with the environment of these minority populations. As a result, in order to bring this community on par with the rest of the community, we recommend the following points:

- Invest to encourage them in developing traditional skills specializations including making footwear, utensils such as pots, pans, knives, spoons, and farm implements and hairdressing, and create modern centers to help them hone their specific skills because this will enable these people to compete and adapt to the market.

- For the eradication of poverty, unemployment is one of the most priority strategies. However, the unemployment rate is going high for the last two decades. Other things constant, for FGM, was successfully regarded as outlaw unemployment was increase to those who were carrying out this ritual custom. As a result, it becomes necessary to train FGM involvers with alternative skills for income generation. Besides, prostitute women in Dami need to be created jobs through life skill training from us as a way to prevent being sexual victims.
- Those who lost their businesses in the Wahan market fire and had Dahabshil Bank loans must be paid back because they are unable to pay.
- Launch a global movement to support these communities, incorporating regional and district political engagement, public workers, and non-governmental groups. This enables these minority populations to seek out and catch up with other majority communities, where they are far behind.
- Members of this group should be included in all six regions' police, security forces, and judiciary
- Incorporate the needs of this communities into the national development plans of the government and the international aid groups.
- Set up a budget by the government and the INGOs for the development of these minority communities to be subsidized, including education and small business. This allows these minority communities to reach out to other areas majority communities they are far behind.
- They require a high school. Because the village lacks a high school, primary school graduates must attend distant high schools.

Acknowledgement

As Bulsho Humanitarian organization (BHO), it is a great pleasure for us to

acknowledge the excellent cooperation we have with World Vision and Dahabshil bank. The community we serve has greatly appreciated World Vision and Dahabshil bank due to the helpful support that it provides. They remember and keep in heart their supports.

World Vision

As BHO, we would like to highlight four areas that World Vision has done to assist the most vulnerable minorities we serve.

Advocacy

It held a seminar for 15 men and women to train them in advocating for the rights of the communities they represent. After convenient three-days training transformed and increased the ability of advocacy of the trainees, and immediately became empowered to advocate the rights of the community they represented. For instance, it is noteworthy that these trained members dared to meet both the vice President and former Mayor, Abdirahman Soolteeko.

Supply of school and office equipment

World vision assisted with 100 school seats and a number of school bags to Daami primary School and 25 office seats to Bulsho. It has improved the school because the number of students has increased. For example, the number of students reached 450, while it was 100 or less than previously. Therefore, this community is very grateful for the unprecedented support they have received from World Vision. As a result, they have awarded certificates of appreciation to World Vision, the Minister of Education, and Bulsho.

Donated 300 pairs of women's shoes

World Vision has donated 300 pairs of women's shoes to this minority community that we serve. The donation has become very touching in the hearts of the women because it was a basic need that would be difficult for a human being to function without it. Also, these shoes were modern, beautiful

and very pleasing to the young girls.

Health: Treat Mohamed Khadar Said

World Vision collaborated with us to treat Mohamed Khadar Said, a 10-years old boy hit by a car. It is noteworthy that the wrecked vehicle escaped. Besides, the boy was an orphan with neither mother nor father.

World Vision assisted Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs (MOLSA) in consultative meeting on minority communities' political participation and power-sharing in Somaliland government. In conclusion, we would like to highlight here how the minority community in Somaliland has not forgotten the things that WV has supported to improve their lives.

Dahabshil Bank

We would also like to express our gratitude to Dahabshil Bank. Dahabshil has made investments in over 200 small businesses, including barbers and hairdressers, shoemakers, tumal, and small women's businesses. It also made an investment in young people by providing them with work vehicles. Dahabshil's loan investment has aided in poverty alleviation.

MOELSA, under the Abdirashid, DG

However, the government's performance is not nothing. One of the important government initiatives has been the involvement of the Ministry of Labor, Social Affairs, and Family Affairs in recruiting persons from these marginalized communities. For example, AbdiRashid, the ministry's director, is in charge of 15 women hired by

Team of the Assessment

Abdinasir Hassan Timoweyne, Executive Director of Bulsho, compiled, wrote, and edited this assessment.

Deeq Dahir Farah and their team gathered the information. The information was gathered from members of the four village committees as well as ordinary citizens.

People from many different parts of the community attended the focus group discussion, including village committees, traditional leaders, religious leaders, politicians, women, and young people.

About the study

This assessment, which is not plagiarism and is based on facts and the truth, has been published in order to raise the voice of Somaliland's marginalised minority communities. It needs to be reviewed and edited on a voluntary basis. There is also a need to fund conferences for its presentation in Somaliland's six regions.

Anyone is welcome to contribute.

Budget plan					
Expenses	Unit type	Quantity	# of units	Unit rate (US\$)	Total Cost in (US\$)
project Budget Plan					
Discription Of Project Budget Plan					
Consultative meeting Facilitators	Days	2	1	\$ 300.00	\$600.00
Refreshment and lunch (day 1)	Days	2	100	\$ 15.00	\$3000.00
Participants perdiium	Days	2	100	10	\$2000.00
Accommodation, meal and transportation cost for guest from Awdal(5 people), Togdheer(7) and Saxil (3)	Days	2	15	\$50.00	\$1500
Projector Rent	Days	2	1	\$ 30.00	\$60.00
Flipchart	Days		5	\$20	\$100.00
Banners	Days		1	\$ 50.00	\$50.00
Notebooks	Days	box	9	\$6.00	\$54.00
Whiteboard marker	Days	box	1	\$3	\$3.00
Publishing of the assessment	Days		120	\$ 3.00	\$ 360.00
Venue Rent	Days	2		\$ 250	\$500.00
Media Cost	Days		4	\$ 150.00	\$600.00
Admin Cost			5%	\$ 441.35.00	\$441.35.00
Project Total Cost					\$ 9268.35

Annex

Questionnaire

A. Socio-economic status

1. How much money does your family spend each day on bills?
 - a. \$0
 - b. \$1-2
 - c. \$2-3
 - d. \$3-4
 - e. \$4-5

2. How many people in your family are employed?
 - a. 0
 - b. 1
 - c. 2
 - d. 3
 - e. 4
 - f. 5
2. How many people in your family are employed by the government?
 - a. 0
 - b. 1
 - c. 2
 - d. 3
 - e. 4
 - f. 5

3. How many women in your family are employed?
 - a. 0
 - b. 1
 - c. 2
 - d. 3
 - e. 4
 - f. 5

B. Education

1. How many children are there in the family?
 - a. 0
 - b. 1 -3
 - c. 1-5
 - d. 1-8
 - e. 1-10
 - f. 1-15

2. How many children in your family go to school? ()
3. How many females do you have in your family? ()

- 4. What is the girls' level of education? ()
- 5. If they do not complete the education, what is the reason?

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

C. Security

- 2. How safe is it in your village?
 - a. Good
 - b. bad
 - c. b. neutral

- 3. If insecurity exists, what are some of the insecurities that threaten you?

- 1.
.....
- 2.
.....
- 3.
.....
- 4.
.....
- 5.
.....

- 3. What is the source of insecurity in your community?

- 1.
.....
- 2.
.....
- 3.
.....
- 4.
.....
- 5.
.....

- 4. How are you treated by the police and the courts?
 - a. Similar to other communities
 - b. Discrimination
 - c. Moderate

D. Water

1. What about your water supply?
 - a. It is good,
 - b. bad,
 - c. neutral.

2. How much water do you get in a day?
 - a. 0 litters
 - b. 5 litter
 - c. 20 litres
 - d. b 40 litres
 - e. 60 litres 80 litres

3. Where do they get their water?
 - a. well
 - b. tank truck
 - c. donkey-tank
 - d. tap

4. How many times a week do you get water from the tap?
 - a. 0
 - b. 1-2
 - c. 2-3
 - d. 3-5

E. Health service

1. Health services are poor all over the country; how are you different?
 - a. I am superior to

 - b. We are in a worse situation than the rest of society.

 - c. We are similar.

2. Does the village have a mother-and-baby nursery?
 - a. Yes

 - b. No

3. If this is the case, how good or bad is the service?
 - a. good

 - b. bad

- c. extremely poor
- d. excellent

Focus group discussion

Questions

Discrimination against Gabooye communities is a long-standing issue. Has anything changed, and is the situation better than before in terms of issues like

1. Law and order: police stations and courts
2. Equality of access to public services such as education, health, electricity, water, and roads.
3. Politics: political participation, such as council participation
4. Opportunities for government employees to participate
5. Inclusion of your community's needs in the national development plan
6. Participation in international aid organisations
7. Interaction with others
8. The effect of Wahan market on your community's businesses?

Participants

Group discussion members were:

1. Chief Ahmed Abdi,
traditional leader, member of the Dami District Judicial Committee,
Tel. +25263 4126568
2. Chief Adan Kadaf,
traditional leader, member of the Dami District Judicial Committee,
Tel. +252634111027
3. Ubah Abdilahi Hirsi spokeswoman of Dami Women's Committee,
4. Gudoon Omer Hassan,
educated woman,
Tel. +25263 4521716
5. Suldan Maxamuud Xuseen
Tel. +252634108704
6. Osman Arab Hersi,
Tel. +252634334253
7. Abdisaaq husein Mousa,
Tel. +252633816182,
8. Asiya Abdilahi Haji.
Tel. 25263 4822860,
9. Layla Dahir Faraax,
Tel. +252634456529
10. Jamac Aarb AHmed
Tel. 252634477133